

Comparison between lower-cost and conventional eddy covariance setups for CO₂ and evapotranspiration measurements above monocropping and agroforestry systems

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ABSTRACT

Novel, lower-cost setups of eddy covariance systems may offer a potential solution to the spatial replication problem of single flux towers. Prior to their widespread application, it is essential to conduct comprehensive testing against conventional eddy covariance setups to ensure the accuracy and precision of the measurements. In this study, we performed a comparison between three lower-cost eddy covariance setups based on lower-cost (approximately 33 % of the cost of a conventional infrared gas analyzer) slow-response carbon dioxide (CO₂) and relative humidity (RH) sensors and a conventional eddy covariance setup for measuring carbon dioxide and evapotranspiration (ET) fluxes above a monocropping agricultural site in Northern Germany. The fluxes measured by these setups were further compared with a fourth lower-cost eddy covariance setup in an adjacent agroforestry field. The three lower-cost setups demonstrated satisfactory agreement with the conventional eddy covariance setup, with the slopes of the linear regression models for the 30-min flux time series ranging from 0.95 to 1.05 (R² from 0.88 to 0.92) for CO₂ fluxes and from 0.78 to 0.99 (R² from 0.7 to 0.85) for latent heat (LE) fluxes. All lower-cost setups reproduced well diel and seasonal CO₂ flux and ET dynamics. Furthermore, the lower-cost eddy covariance setups were able to measure ecosystem differences between agroforestry and monocropping, with differences in fluxes between both land uses being higher than differences between different setups. Despite the necessity for enhanced spectral corrections and the higher uncertainty associated with the lower-cost setups, the findings of this study illustrate the potential of these lower-cost setups to validate and replicate conventional eddy covariance setups, thereby enhancing the spatial representativity of measurements of energy, trace gases and momentum exchanges between terrestrial ecosystems and the atmosphere.

1. Introduction

Micrometeorological measurements have become the most important tool to understand the exchange of energy, trace gases such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), and H₂O between agro-ecosystems and the atmosphere. In the last decades, micrometeorological measurements have provided valuable insights into a number of key areas, including CO₂ uptake (Davis et al., 2010), plant-water relations (Suyker and Verma, 2012), water use efficiency (Zhou et al., 2015), and the response of crops to environmental changes, such as those induced by climate change (Xiao et al., 2013). The central micrometeorological approach is the

eddy covariance (EC) method which directly measures the net exchange of energy, trace gases, and momentum between a terrestrial ecosystem and the atmosphere (Baldocchi, 2003). The measurements are based on the calculation of the covariance between the vertical wind component and an atmospheric scalar, such as the CO₂ or H₂O concentration or air temperature. The EC technique is based on the detection of turbulent eddies of varying sizes and frequencies, which transport energy and matter in both vertical and horizontal directions across the atmosphere-surface interface. In order to sample the relevant frequency range of the turbulent energy spectrum, the EC technique requires the use of fast-response instruments with measurement frequencies typically

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≥ 10 Hz (Aubinet et al., 2012).

The spatial replication of EC measurements has been largely overlooked due to the high costs associated with fast-response instrumentation, particularly the necessary infrared gas analyzer (IRGA) (Hill et al., 2017). This is based on the assumption that EC measurements integrate over an assumed homogeneous land surface. In practice, however, field measurements are typically conducted in ecologically interesting landscapes, that do not necessarily fulfill the requirement of spatially homogeneous sources and sinks of, for example, CO₂. This includes small-scale agricultural fields (Davis et al., 2010), forests with heterogeneous stands (Soubie et al., 2016), and agroforestry systems (Markwitz et al., 2020). The precise location of the flux tower within the landscape of investigation introduces a number of potential biases, which remain unclear (Hill et al., 2017). Even when two flux towers are paired, the spatial replication is insufficient to permit a statistically robust assessment of turbulent fluxes in a heterogeneous landscape (Hill et al., 2017; Hollinger and Richardson, 2005). To enhance the spatial replication level of EC measurements it would be advantageous to expand the number of EC setups within the same ecosystem of interest.

Lower-cost (LC) - EC systems can increase spatial replication without increasing costs in terms of initial funding and maintenance (Hill et al., 2017). In recent years, LC-EC setups for measuring evapotranspiration (ET) (Cunliffe et al., 2022; Hill et al., 2017; Markwitz and Siebicke, 2019) and CO₂ fluxes (Cunliffe et al., 2022; Hill et al., 2017) have been developed and tested. In all cases, the conventional high-frequency IRGA (CON-EC) was replaced by alternative LC instruments, such as thermohygrometers, relative humidity cells and CO₂ IRGAs. The main difference between the LC gas analyzers and the conventional IRGA was their markedly slower response time, which amplified the magnitude of the spectral energy losses in the high-frequency range of the turbulent power spectrum (Cunliffe et al., 2022; Hill et al., 2017). It is therefore necessary to correct for these losses, which results in higher uncertainties compared to CON-EC measurements, where the spectral attenuation due to the use of faster response instruments is usually lower (Moncrieff et al., 1997). Nevertheless, the performance of the LC-EC setups was demonstrated to be within the typical uncertainty associated with EC studies (10 % for sensible heat and 20–30 % for latent heat and trace gases; Finkelstein and Sims, 2001), despite the technique's requirement of fast-response instruments. Hill et al. (2017) showed a 3 % overestimation and 2 % underestimation of CO₂ fluxes from two different LC-EC setups, compared to CON-EC, respectively; and a 6 % overestimation of LE fluxes. Markwitz and Siebicke (2019) showed results in a range from 14 % underestimation to 8 % overestimation of LE fluxes, compared to CON-EC, for different sites.

The application of LC-EC measurements is of particular interest in heterogeneous agricultural landscapes, such as those small-scale field sizes or agroforestry systems. Agroforestry systems comprise combinations of croplands or grasslands with cultivated trees, designated for food production or livestock feed and biomass for energy production, timber or other tree products (e.g.: fruits and nuts), respectively (Cardinael et al., 2021; Nair, 1985). The lower-cost of LC-EC setups allows for the deployment of multiple EC setups, which offers the opportunity to better capture the spatial variability of fluxes, thereby improving the measurements of energy and trace gas exchange above agroforestry systems (Markwitz and Siebicke, 2019). Nevertheless, the application of prototype LC-EC systems requires meticulous evaluation to guarantee optimal measurement quality. In particular, studies comparing different ecosystems (e.g., agroforestry versus crop monoculture) require lower instrument differences compared to differences within or across the ecosystems of interest, to ensure that the LC-EC setups are capable of resolving the variability of fluxes across sites.

In the current study, we tested the hypothesis that flux differences between different EC setups (e.g., LC-EC and conventional EC) are lower than differences between different land uses (agroforestry vs. monocropping). The agroforestry system under investigation is designated as a Short Rotation Alley Cropping (SRAC) and represents a highly

heterogeneous ecosystem (Markwitz et al., 2020). It was compared to an adjacent monocropping system (MC). A comparison was made between a set of three closed-path LC-EC setups to a conventional EC setup. Furthermore, an additional LC-EC setup was running in the adjacent SRAC system during the measurement campaign. The following objectives were addressed: (i) to evaluate the performance of three LC-EC setups in comparison to a conventional EC setup, (ii) to compare LC-EC setups above MC and SRAC, and to evaluate their longer-term capability to measure fluxes of CO₂ and LE above the studied sites and (iii) to understand different error sources and uncertainties that the use of LC-EC setups might add to the EC technique, as well as propose methods to correct for them.

2. Methodology

2.1. Description of the site and measurement campaign

The study site is located at 52.33° N, 10.63° E in Wendhausen (Lehre), Lower Saxony (Germany). The elevation above sea level is 80 m. The mean annual precipitation for the reference period 1991–2020 is 617.9 mm; the mean annual temperature is 9.9 °C (Deutscher Wetterdienst, 2023). The landscape is characterized by a flat topography, divided in two distinct agricultural systems: a monocropping (MC) system and a SRAC system (see Fig. 1). The trees grown in the SRAC are aspen poplar (*Populus tremula* L.), with harvest typically occurring in cycles of 3–6 years, the most recent of which occurred in 2020. At the time of the measurement campaign, trees were between 3 and 4 m tall. The crops grown in the MC area and in between the tree rows at the SRAC are maintained consistently across both sites and follow a yearly varying rotation scheme, as well as the same soil cultivation.

The SRAC system is divided into two equal-sized sections, with six tree rows in the northern section and three tree rows in the southern section. The tree rows are 10 m wide and 225 m long, with the crop rows situated between them. The crop rows are 48 m wide in the northern part and 96 m wide in the southern part. Crops grown during the measurement campaign were barley, rapeseed, and corn, distributed from west to east (Fig. 1). The rapeseed was harvested on 14 July 2022, while the corn was harvested on 31 August 2022, after the measurement campaign.

The measurement campaign took place from 11 April 2022 to 11 August 2022.

2.2. Instrumental setup

There were two measuring stations at the site. The first one was situated at the MC and included three lower-cost EC setups and one conventional EC setup. The second was located at the SRAC system and included one lower-cost EC setup (Fig. 1). The height of the stations was 3.5 m at the MC and 10 m at the SRAC. Both stations were solar-powered, with the installation comprising monocrystalline solar panels (model 3-01-001245, from Offgridtec GmbH, Eggenfelden, Germany), lithium batteries (type S12/130, code NGS0120130HSOCA, from Exide Technologies GmbH, Bidingen, Germany) and solar charger controllers (model PR 10–30, from KATEK Memmingen GmbH, Memmingen, Germany). With regards to the characterization of footprints, more than 70 % of the measured fluxes originated from the ecosystem of interest in the case of the SRAC, while in the MC more than 90 % of the fluxes originated from the MC site (Fig. 1). All the setups at the MC showed similar flux footprint climatology since this is dependent on the measurement location and wind data. All the setups shared the same sonic anemometer.

2.2.1. Ancillary meteorological measurements

Standard meteorological variables were measured at both stations with identical instruments, including air temperature and relative humidity at 2 m height, air pressure at 1.5 m height, precipitation at 1 m

Fig. 1. Satellite view and land cover classification of the experimental site, along with the position of the EC stations and the contour lines of the footprint climatology of the stations. The area in red corresponds to the SRAC system, while the area in blue corresponds to the MC system. The star and the cross indicate the location of the EC stations at the SRAC and the MC, respectively. The contour lines for the flux footprint climatology correspond to the 70, 80, and 90 % flux contribution for the LC-EC at the SRAC (orange lines) and the setups at the MC (black lines). The footprint analysis was conducted on coincident periods for all setups at the MC, hence only one footprint is shown. The figure was created using QGIS v. 3.22, with the aerial map source from Google Satellite Maps. © Google 2023.

height, the soil heat flux with two heat flux plates at 5 cm depth, and radiation (short wave incoming and outgoing radiation and net radiation) at 3 m (MC) or 9 m (SRAC) height, respectively (see Table 1 for more information). The meteorological data were recorded every 10 s and stored on a CR1000X datalogger (Campbell Scientific, Inc. Logan, UT, USA). All dataloggers were connected to a Raspberry Pi via an Ethernet connection for the purposes of data backup and remote access. During the measurement campaign, there were no data gaps at the MC plot. Data gaps at the SRAC plot occurred 12 % of the time and were filled with data from the MC plot by linear regression.

2.2.2. Conventional EC (CON-EC) setup

The 3D wind velocity field was measured with a u-SONIC-3 Omni sonic anemometer (METEK GmbH, Elmshorn, Germany) at a height of 3.5 m (MC) or 10 m (SRAC), respectively, and a measurement frequency of 20 Hz.

CO₂ and H₂O_v mole fractions were measured with the enclosed-path infrared gas analyzer Li-7200 (LI-COR Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA) at a frequency of 20 Hz. The intake tube of the Li-7200 was 1 m in length, with an inner diameter of 8.2 mm and a flow rate of 15 L min⁻¹ (Table 2). The air intake was located below the sonic anemometer with a vertical separation of 15 cm between the air intake and the center of the sonic anemometer, an eastward separation of 5 cm, and a northward separation of 0 cm.

2.2.3. LC-EC setup

The LC-EC setup included the same sonic anemometer as the EC setup (model u-SONIC-3 Omni, from METEK), but the conventional IRGA for CO₂ and H₂O_v concentration measurements was replaced by a custom-made closed-path gas analyzer setup, comprising a GMP343

(Vaisala Oyj, Helsinki, Finland) for CO₂ molar density measurements and a relative humidity (RH) cell HIH-4000 (Honeywell International Inc., Charlotte, North Carolina, USA) for RH measurements (Fig. 2). The cost of the LC-EC IRGA was approximately 33 % of that of the conventional IRGA. This setup was analogous to the setup deployed by Cunliffe et al. (2022). Subsequently, CO₂ and H₂O dry mole fractions were calculated from CO₂ molar density and RH, respectively. The water vapor dry mole fraction was calculated from RH, cell pressure, and cell temperature, using the derivation of Markwitz and Siebicke (2019). The air intake was protected by a glass cup to prevent contamination of the tubes and was located below the sonic anemometer with a vertical separation of 20 cm and no separation for eastward and northward directions. The sampled air was directed to the different LC-EC enclosures, located at the bottom of the tower (Fig. 2, right), using Synflex 1300 tubes (1300-M0603, Eaton Corporation, Dublin, Ireland) with an inner diameter of 4 mm and varying lengths (e.g. 3, 4 and 4.5 m at the MC site and 10 m at the SRAC site) depending on the height of the tower and the location of the box containing the LC-EC enclosure (Table 2). Two stainless steel filters with a pore size of 2 μm (SS-4FW-2, Swagelok, Solon, Ohio, USA) were installed to prevent the ingress of dust and other pollutants into the measuring system. The air was pulled by a micro diaphragm gas sampling pump (model NMP830KND-C, KNF Neuberger Inc., Trenton, New Jersey, USA), which maintained a nominal flow rate of 2.0 L·min⁻¹. The LC-EC enclosure (Fig. 2, left) included the pump, a differential pressure transmitter to estimate flow rates (NTC MPX5100DP, NXP USA Inc., Austin, Texas, USA), a heater which aimed to reduce the risk of water condensation in the last section of the tubing system, an absolute pressure transmitter (NTC MPX5100AP, NXP USA Inc., Austin, Texas, USA) and finally the IRGA consisting of the GMP343 CO₂ sensor, the HIH-4000 RH chip and a T-type thermocouple (Omega

Table 1
Measured variables, instruments, and instrument type at the site.

Measured variable	Units	Instrument	Model	Company
Precipitation, ppt	mm	Precipitation transmitter	5.4032.35.007	Thies Clima, Göttingen, Germany
Atmospheric pressure, p	bar	Baro transmitter	3.1157.10.000	Thies Clima, Göttingen, Germany
Net radiation, R_N	$W \cdot m^{-2}$	Net radiometer	NR Lite2	Kipp & Zonen, B.V., Delft, The Netherlands
Shortwave incoming radiation, SW_{in}	$W \cdot m^{-2}$	Pyranometer	CMP3	Kipp & Zonen, B.V., Delft, The Netherlands
Shortwave outgoing radiation, SW_{out}	$W \cdot m^{-2}$	Pyranometer	CMP3	Kipp & Zonen, B.V., Delft, The Netherlands
Relative humidity, RH	%	Hygro-thermo transmitter-compact	1.1105.54.160	Thies Clima, Göttingen, Germany
Air temperature, T_a	°C	Hygro-thermo transmitter-compact	1.1105.54.160	Thies Clima, Göttingen, Germany
CO ₂ molar density, LC setup, r_c	$\mu\text{mol}(\text{CO}_2) \cdot \text{m}^{-3}(\text{air})$	Infrared gas analyzer	GMP343	Vaisala Oyj, Helsinki, Finland
RH (from LC setup)	%	Relative humidity sensor	HIH-4000	Honey-well, Charlotte, North Carolina, USA
CO ₂ dry mole fraction, conventional setup, r_c	$\mu\text{mol}(\text{CO}_2) \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}(\text{dry air})$	Infrared gas analyzer	Li-7200	LI-COR Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA
H ₂ O dry mole fraction, conventional setup, r_v	$\text{mmol}(\text{H}_2\text{O}) \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}(\text{dry air})$	Infrared gas analyzer	Li-7200	LI-COR Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA
Soil heat flux, G	$W \cdot m^{-2}$	Soil heat flux plates	HFP01	Hukseflux, Delft, The Netherlands
Wind velocity components, (u, v, w)	$\text{cm} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$	Ultrasonic anemometer	uSONIC-3 Omni	METEK GmbH, Elmshorn, Germany

Table 2
Estimated time response of CO₂ and H₂O, tube length, tube diameter and flow rate for the three LC-EC setups and the CON-EC setup at the MC, and the LC-EC setup at the SRAC. The time response of H₂O corresponds to the lowest and the highest RH classes as estimated from the co-spectra, although in some cases there were missing values due to the lack of sufficient data. In order to calculate the transfer function, a fit was employed to explain the dependence of $\tau_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ on RH.

	LC-EC-I	LC-EC-II	LC-EC-III	CON-EC	LC-EC-SRAC
τ_{CO_2} (s)	1.37	1.17	1.44	0.16	7.3
$\tau_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ (s)	1.88; 4.54	1.82; 6.36	3.4; 4.55	0.21; 1.38	2.44; 7.3
Tube length (m)	3.0	4.0	4.5	1.0	10.0
Tube diameter (m)	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.0082	0.004
Flow rate ($\text{L} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$)	2.0	1.5	1.2	15.0	1.8
Vertical/Northward/ Eastward separation (m)	0.2/0/ 0	0.2/0/ 0	0.2/0/ 0	0.2/0/ 0.05	0.2/0/0

Engineering Inc., Norwalk, Connecticut, USA) to measure cell temperature. The HIH-4000 RH cell and the T-type thermocouple were affixed to the measuring cell of the GMP343 via the use of a plastic cover (labeled “Irga enclosure” in Fig. 2, left). Absolute pressure, RH, and cell temperature were employed to correct the CO₂ dry mole fraction and to calculate the H₂O_v dry mole fraction subsequently (see Section 2.4.1).

The GMP343 CO₂ sensor was an IRGA with a time response of 1.36 s and a nominal accuracy of $\pm (5 \mu\text{mol}_{\text{CO}_2} \cdot \text{mol}_{\text{dry air}}^{-1} + 2\% \text{ of reading})$ for the 2000 ppm measurement range. The HIH-4000 RH cell was a capacitive sensing chip with a time response of 5 s and an accuracy of $\pm 3.5\%$. The absolute pressure transmitter exhibits an accuracy of ± 1.5 kPa and a time response of 1 ms. The type T thermocouple exhibits an accuracy of ± 1.8 K and a time response of 0.2 s.

The measurements of the wind components, CO₂ molar density, RH, cell pressure, and cell temperature were logged at 2 Hz frequency on CR6 dataloggers (Campbell Scientific, Inc. Logan, UT, USA). Each LC-EC setup was equipped with its own datalogger. The data from the conventional EC setup were logged on the same CR6 datalogger as for one of the LC-EC setups at the MC. The wind data were logged in real time on the different dataloggers using an RS-232 split of the signal (Bies, 2021).

The various EC setups were named as follows: LC-EC-I, LC-EC-II, LC-EC-III, and CON-EC (the conventional EC setup) at the MC plot; and LC-EC-SRAC at the SRAC plot.

2.3. Calibration and problems during the campaign

Prior to installation, the GMP343 sensors from the LC-EC-II and the LC-EC-III setups, as well as the Li-7200 analyzer, underwent calibration in accordance to a two-point calibration protocol. At the LC-EC setups, CO₂ was calibrated exclusively, while at the CON-EC setup both CO₂ and H₂O_v were calibrated. For the calibration of CO₂ of the GMP343 sensors and the Li-7200, we once applied a zero gas (N₂) and a span gas of 407.13 $\mu\text{mol} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ CO₂. For the calibration of the water vapor mole fraction from the Li-7200 we used a dew point generator (LI-610, LI-COR Inc., Lincoln, USA) and applied a water vapor mole fraction according to a dew point temperature of 10 °C. On May 3, 2022, a spare, calibrated sensor was installed in place of the GMP343 sensor from the LC-EC-I setup.

During the measurement campaign, frequent inspections of the instruments were performed. These included flow rate checks, filter replacement, cleaning of the intake tubes, and cleaning of the lenses from the GMP343s. By the middle of the measurement campaign, the Li-7200 experienced a drop in signal strength below 80 % (the recommended threshold by the manufacturer), with values ranging from 60 to 70 %. This was due to an increasing contamination of the lens.

It was observed that the flow rate was not consistently maintained at the nominal value (2 L min⁻¹) in the LC-EC setups due to occasional filter clogging. The flow rate was approximately 1.5 L min⁻¹ (25 % lower) for the LC-EC-II and 1.2 L min⁻¹ (40 % lower) for the LC-EC-III setups due to the longer tubes. In all three cases, the motion within the tubes and the measuring cell was not turbulent, with estimated Reynolds numbers of 710 and 360 for flow rates of 2.0 L min⁻¹ (nominal) and 1.0 L min⁻¹ (highly clogged filters), respectively.

2.4. Data processing

2.4.1. Pre-processing

No pre-processing was applied to the CON-EC data prior to flux computation. For the LC-EC setups the following pre-processing steps were carried out:

- (a) H₂O dry mole fraction calculation. The wet mole fraction of H₂O ($\chi_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, in $\text{mmol}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} \cdot \text{mol}_{\text{air}}^{-1}$) was derived following Markwitz and Siebicke (2019) with relative humidity, cell temperature, and cell pressure as input. To reduce the noise on covariance when

Fig. 2. (Left) Components of the LC-EC setup enclosure consisting of a differential pressure cell, a pump providing the airflow, a heater with an RH cell and a thermocouple, an absolute pressure cell, a CR6 datalogger, the IRGA measurement cell including the GMP343 CO₂ sensor, the RH sensor, and the thermocouple and a regulated 12 V power supply. The direction of airflow is indicated by the blue arrows. (Right) EC station at the MC plot with the uSONIC-3 Omni sonic anemometer (1), the Li-7200 IRGA (2), the Li-7200 analyzer interface unit (3), the Li-7200 flow-module box (4), the three LC-EC systems (5, 6, 7), the thermohygrometer (8), the radiation sensors (including two global radiation sensors and one net radiometer) (9), and the box with the CR1000X datalogger and the Raspberry Pi (10). The zoomed image in the top right corner of the display shows the air intake for CON-EC (11) and LC-EC (12) setups.

calculating the fluxes, a moving average with a window of 5 min was applied to the cell pressure. The dry mole fraction (or mixing ratio, r_v) was calculated from the wet mole fraction (χ_{H_2O}) as follows:

$$r_v = \frac{\chi_{H_2O}}{1 - \chi_{H_2O}} \left(\text{mmol}_{H_2O} \cdot \text{mol}_{\text{dry air}}^{-1} \right)$$

- (b) *Removal of wrong RH measurements.* Unrealistic RH values, caused by condensation following some heavy rain events, were removed from the raw, high-frequency data.
- (c) *Conversion of CO₂ measurements from the GMP343 to dry mole fraction.* The CO₂ dry mole fraction, r_c ($\mu\text{mol}_{CO_2} \cdot \text{mol}_{\text{dry air}}^{-1}$), was calculated from the molar density, provided by the GMP343, using an iterative equation from Vaisala (2023), which incorporates sensor-specific parameters to account for the varying RH and pressure values inside the measuring cell.

2.4.2. Flux computation

2.4.2.1. Derivation of fluxes from the CON-EC setup. The CO₂ (F_{CO_2}) and LE fluxes were calculated using EddyUH, a software for eddy covariance flux calculation developed at the University of Helsinki (Mammarella et al., 2016). A coordinate rotation was performed in accordance to the double rotation method. Time lags were calculated by performing cross-covariance maximization between CO₂ or H₂O dry mole fraction and vertical wind velocity, within a predefined window with minimum and maximum limits of 1 and 5 s, respectively, for the time estimations (Mammarella et al., 2009; Markwitz and Siebicke, 2019). Spikes in the raw data were removed using limits for the absolute difference between consecutive data points. The quality of the fluxes was assessed using the nine-step (1–9) flagging method proposed by Foken et al. (2004). Lateral separation effects were accounted for in accordance to the recommendations set by Horst and Lenschow (2009). Fluxes were corrected for frequency losses using the formulations by Rannik and Vesala (1999) in the low-frequency range and by Mammarella et al. (2009) in the high-frequency range, respectively.

2.4.2.2. Derivation of fluxes from the LC-EC setup. The fluxes from the LC-EC setup were computed using EddyUH. The settings for computing fluxes from the LC-EC setup were analogous to those employed in the CON-EC setup, with the exception of the time lag optimization procedure and the fit of the spectral transfer functions for the high-frequency corrections. The time lags were also calculated via cross-covariance maximization, as for the CON-EC, using windows of 2–10 s for CO₂ and 2 to 20 s for H₂O. Nevertheless, unrealistically low or high time lags were attained for certain periods, corresponding to low magnitude fluxes. To prevent these time lags from influencing the flux calculations, they were replaced with fluxes calculated for fixed values of the time lag, corresponding to the peaks of the density plots of all previously estimated time lags. Fluxes were replaced for CO₂ flux values below $4 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (absolute value) and for LE flux values below 10 W m^{-2} . The high-frequency losses were restored following the experimental method of Mammarella et al. (2009). Given that the time response estimation of CO₂ was very close to the nominal value of 1.36 s, this value was employed for calculating the transfer functions of CO₂.

2.4.2.3. High-frequency corrections after Mammarella et al. (2009). The spectral transfer functions were calculated from the co-spectra of CO₂ and H₂O, employing the Eqs. (6) and (7) in the Mammarella et al. (2009) paper. The co-spectra utilized for the estimation of time responses of CO₂ and H₂O were ensemble averages derived from the good quality co-spectra classified into six wind direction (for CO₂) or RH (for H₂O) bins. Good quality co-spectra for transfer function calculation were selected from fluxes exceeding certain thresholds (below $-2 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the CON-EC setup and $-6 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for the LC-EC setups, for CO₂ flux, and above 20 W m^{-2} , for LE flux). The time response estimated for CO₂ was calculated as a weighted median across all wind direction bins. For all LC-EC setups, this value was found to be very close to the nominal value of 1.36 s (Table 2), hence the nominal value was used for calculating spectral correction factors. In the case of H₂O, the time response of the sensor was calculated for different RH classes and a fit was used to explain its dependence with RH. This was then employed to calculate spectral correction factors across the entire range of RH conditions for single covariances.

2.4.3. Post-processing

The post-processing analysis entailed the following steps applied to the previously computed fluxes, both from the CON-EC and LC-EC setups:

- Friction velocity (u_*) filter for CO_2 and LE fluxes.** The CO_2 and LE fluxes were filtered according to a u_* -threshold, calculated for each setup using the REddyProc R-package (Wutzler et al., 2018). Given that the u_* threshold estimates differed slightly between the setups, the highest u_* threshold (0.1 m s^{-1}) across all four setups at the MC plot was selected as the threshold for all the other datasets. At the SRAC, the estimated threshold was 0.15 m s^{-1} .
- Quality flags for all fluxes.** Data with a quality flag greater than 6, as defined by the flagging procedure of Foken et al. (2004), were excluded (corresponding to weak or non-existent turbulence). This flagging procedure assigns quality flags from 1 to 9, with 1 representing the highest quality data and 9 representing the lowest quality data.
- Outlier detection method to cancel data out of range.** A median absolute deviation (MAD) filter was applied to CO_2 and LE fluxes, with data that did not fall within the specified range being rejected. The MAD of a collection of samples (time series of fluxes in our case) was calculated in accordance with the definition proposed by Huber (1981). This involved calculating the median of the absolute deviations of each individual value around the median of the time series, multiplied by a constant (Leys et al., 2013). The following criteria were employed to determine the acceptability of data:

$$\left| \frac{F_{\text{CO}_2} - M_{\text{CO}_2}}{\text{MAD}_{\text{CO}_2}} \right| \leq 5.5 \text{ for } \text{CO}_2$$

$$-1.4 \leq \frac{F_{\text{LE}} - M_{\text{LE}}}{\text{MAD}_{\text{LE}}} \leq 5.5 \text{ for LE}$$

With MAD and M the median absolute deviation and the median, respectively, of the complete time series.

Following the application of steps (a) to (c), between 67 and 71 % of the data remained in the case of CO_2 fluxes and between 62 and 69 % in the case of LE fluxes.

- Footprint climatology analysis.** The footprint analysis was conducted using the model of Kljun et al. (2015), implemented in the open-source Python code (<https://footprint.kljun.net/download.php>). The model was fed with wind variables and atmospheric characteristics derived from the flux computation, as well as the boundary layer height from the ERA-5 re-analysis data (Hersbach et al., 2023).

2.4.4. Data analysis

- Comparison of fluxes from LC-EC and CON-EC.** A reduced major axis (RMA) linear regression model was applied to the data (library *pylr2*, from Python v. 3.9), on the assumption that errors and uncertainties were distributed equally between the CON-EC and LC-EC data. For each comparison (CON-EC versus one of the LC-EC setups) only periods with available data for both setups were selected.
- Energy balance closure (EBC) analysis.** The EBC is defined as the ratio between the sum of the turbulent energy terms ($H + LE$) and the available energy at the land surface, i.e., $R_N - G$ (net radiation R_N ; soil heat flux G). The slope of a (RMA) linear regression

between ($R_N - G$) and ($H + LE$) was interpreted as the EBC. Energy storage terms were not considered in this analysis.

- Statistical analysis.** The Wasserstein distance, which is an effective measure of the distance between statistical distributions (Ramdas et al., 2017), was employed to quantify the differences between LC-EC and CON-EC for CO_2 and LE fluxes. The Wasserstein distance was calculated for each pair of LC-EC and CON-EC in the MC, as well as for the average of the three LC-EC setups in the MC and the LC-EC setup at the SRAC using the Python library *SciPy*.

3. Results

3.1. Meteorological conditions

At both sites, albedo (Fig. 3a) exhibited an increasing trend until the middle of May, followed by a gradual decrease until harvest in the middle of July, when albedo increased sharply. The albedo exhibited small differences between the MC and SRAC plots reflecting the temporal evolution of the crops observed by the radiation sensors at the two towers.

The mean air temperature (Fig. 3b) was found to be higher than the climatological average for the measurement dates for the period 1991–2020, of $15.36 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Deutscher Wetterdienst, 2023), with an average of $15.74 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ during the campaign. The temperature was low at the beginning and it increased until it reached its maximum values at the end of July and beginning of August.

The daily mean relative humidity (Fig. 3b) was low during the measurement campaign and relatively constant, with a slight decrease towards the end of the campaign. The vapor pressure deficit (VPD) exhibited an increase towards the end of the campaign and showed higher variation, with some high peaks in July and August. The precipitation was lower than the climatological average, with a total cumulative sum of 118 mm in that period (Fig. 3c), while the average value for the period 1991–2020 at the nearby weather station from the German weather service in Braunschweig, is 252 mm (Deutscher Wetterdienst, 2023) for the measurement dates. The precipitation occurred predominantly in the second half of May and the beginning of June, with the remainder distributed between a few events in July and August.

3.2. Comparison of LC-EC and CON-EC setups

3.2.1. Mean diel cycle of CO_2 and LE fluxes for the setups at the MC

The net CO_2 fluxes from all the setups at the MC exhibited a similar diel cycle with net CO_2 uptake during the day (negative fluxes), due to the predominance of plant photosynthesis, and a net CO_2 release during the night (positive fluxes), due to plant and soil respiration (Fig. 4a).

The absolute values of CO_2 fluxes from the three LC-EC setups were, however, slightly lower compared to the CON-EC setup, during the daytime, and slightly higher during the nighttime. The difference (mean over the 5 h period from 10:00 to 15:00 h) to the CON-EC CO_2 flux was 2, 7, and 14 % for the LC-EC-I, LC-EC-II, and LC-EC-III, respectively. During the nighttime, the differences between the setups (mean over the 5 h period from 23:00 to 04:00 h) were smaller, with values of 11, 10, and 17 %, respectively.

The mean diel cycle of LE followed a comparable pattern in all setups, with mean fluxes approaching 0 during nighttime and reaching 80 to 130 W m^{-2} during midday (Fig. 4b). The three LC-EC setups measured lower LE fluxes compared to CON-EC, particularly during the daytime, with differences (mean over the 5 h period from 10:00 to 15:00 h) of 5, 14, and 38 % for the LC-EC-I, LC-EC-II, and LC-EC-III, respectively. During the nighttime, the LE fluxes from the LC-EC and the CON-EC setups exhibited larger differences than during daytime, with 20, 32, and 98 % of difference to the CON-EC (mean over the 5 h period from 23:00 to 04:00 h), respectively. However, these differences were affected by the relatively low magnitude of fluxes.

Fig. 3. (a) Albedo of the SRAC and MC, (b) mean daily air temperature (AirT), VPD, and RH, and (c) cumulative daily precipitation (ppt) across the measurement campaign (29 March 2022 to 11 August 2022) from the MC plot.

Fig. 4. Median diel cycles for CO₂ (a) and LE (b) fluxes for all the three LC-EC setups at the MC site, the CON-EC setup at the MC site and the LC-EC setup at the SRAC. For CO₂, positive values indicate a CO₂ release to the atmosphere, and negative values, a CO₂ uptake. For LE, positive values indicate a release of H₂O to the atmosphere via evaporation and transpiration. The error bars indicate the standard error of the mean around the median values for each 30 min period.

3.2.2. Spectra and co-spectra

For the CON-EC setup, both the CO₂ and H₂O spectra followed the sonic temperature spectra in the low-frequency range (Fig. 5a, b). In the inertial subrange, the spectra diverged from the sonic temperature spectra and the theoretical slope of $f^{-2/3}$, showing a more pronounced energy attenuation in the case of H₂O. At the high-frequency end of the spectrum ($f > 10$ Hz), both CO₂ and H₂O spectra showed an increase in spectral energy, a typical indication for white noise.

For the LC-EC setups, the CO₂ spectra exhibited a high degree of similarity across the three setups, yet they did not reproduce the patterns observed in the CON-EC. At the lowest frequencies, the LC-EC CO₂ spectra were close to the sonic temperature spectra, with slightly larger energy content around 10⁻¹ Hz. In the inertial subrange, the spectra of the three LC-EC setups exhibited oscillations that did not align with the theoretical slope line of $f^{-2/3}$. The H₂O spectra exhibited greater variability across the different setups, with two of them, the LC-EC-I and the LC-EC-II, displaying greater similarity in the entire frequency range. The LC-EC-III deviated the most from the other two and from the CON-EC spectra. In contrast to the CO₂ spectra, the LC-EC H₂O spectra followed exhibited a slight but discernible deviation from the theoretical $f^{-2/3}$ slope line, with the energy decrease occurring at lower frequencies than the real inertial subrange. Close to the end of the frequency range LC-EC (before 10¹ Hz) all LC-EC setups exhibited a peak that interrupted the downward slope.

The CO₂ and H₂O co-spectra under stable conditions (with Obukhov length L, 0 m < L < 1000 m) were similar for CON-EC and sonic temperature (Fig. 5c and d), with stronger attenuation for H₂O in the inertial subrange. The CO₂ co-spectra of the LC-EC setups exhibited a greater energy content than the sonic temperature co-spectra throughout the

whole frequency range, while the H₂O co-spectra exhibited higher energy content than the sonic temperature co-spectra at the low- and high-frequency range, but lower in the inertial subrange. For both CO₂ and H₂O, the energy decrease in the inertial subrange was less pronounced than the theoretical $f^{-4/3}$ slope line. The differences across the LC-EC co-spectra were small, just slightly larger in the highest-frequency range.

For unstable conditions (Fig. 5e and f), most pronounced during the day, the co-spectra of the four setups ended at lower frequencies than for stable conditions. The CO₂ and H₂O co-spectra of the CON-EC exhibited a stronger energy attenuation in the inertial subrange than for stable conditions, with a slope more pronounced than the theoretical $f^{-4/3}$ slope line. The CO₂ and H₂O co-spectra of the LC-EC setups were similar to each other and showed higher energy content in the lower frequencies compared to the sonic temperature co-spectra, while in the inertial subrange, the energy content was lower and the energy attenuation was less pronounced than the theoretical $f^{-4/3}$ slope line. The H₂O co-spectra exhibited in this case more discrepancies across the three setups, with the LC-EC-III displaying an earlier energy decrease in the inertial subrange and a less pronounced energy decrease at higher frequencies than the LC-EC-I and the LC-EC-II.

3.2.3. Effect of low- and high-frequency corrections on flux magnitude

For all the LC-EC setups at the MC, the only low-frequency corrected CO₂ fluxes exhibited slopes of 60 %, in relation to the fully corrected fluxes, indicating that the high-frequency correction accounted for 40 % of the fully corrected fluxes (Table 3). The attenuation in the high-frequency range was similar in all three setups. For LE fluxes, the slopes of the only low-frequency corrected data in relation to the fully corrected data were 0.48, 0.51 and 0.4 for the LC-EC-I, LC-EC-II and LC-

Fig. 5. Ensemble average of normalized frequency-weighted power spectra of CO₂ dry mole fraction (a) and H₂O dry mole fraction (b), normalized frequency-weighted co-spectra of CO₂ dry mole fraction (top) and H₂O dry mole fraction (bottom) for stable (c, d) and unstable (e, f) conditions, for all three LC-EC setups and CON-EC at the MC, the LC-EC setup at the SRAC and the sonic temperature, vs. natural frequency (spectra) and normalized frequency (co-spectra). The normalized frequency (n) was calculated by multiplying the natural frequency (f) per the displacement height (z) and dividing by wind speed (u) ($n = fz \cdot u^{-1}$). Power spectra and co-spectra were averaged from quality-checked (co-)spectra, with minimum absolute limits for sensible heat fluxes of 20 W·m⁻² for unstable conditions and 5 W·m⁻² for stable conditions, for LE fluxes of 20 W·m⁻² for unstable conditions and 3 W·m⁻² for stable conditions, for CO₂ fluxes (in absolute value) of 2 μmol·m⁻²·s⁻¹ for unstable conditions and 0.5 μmol·m⁻²·s⁻¹ for stable conditions; and quality flagged periods with 0 and 1, following Foken et al. (2004). The power spectra were averaged across the different stability classes for CO₂ and H₂O, and across RH classes for H₂O. The co-spectra were classified as either under unstable or stable conditions, based on the Obukhov length, L (stable: 0 < L < 1000; unstable: -650 m < L < 0 m). The red line represents the theoretical decrease of the energy in the inertial subrange, as predicted by the theoretical law of Kolmogorov (1991), with a slope of -2/3 when multiplied by the frequency in the case of the spectra (a, b) and a slope of -4/3 in the case of the co-spectra (c, d, e, f) (Foken et al., 2004).

Table 3

Contribution of the low-frequency correction (LFC) and high-frequency correction (HFC) to the total flux for the three LC-EC setups and the CON-EC setup at the MC, for CO₂ and LE fluxes. The values were taken as the difference of the slopes to the unit, in percentage, of the linear model fits of the fully corrected data (x-axis) vs. only high-frequency corrected data and only low-frequency corrected data, respectively. The linear regressions were computed using the reduced major axis method (RMA) from the library *pylr2* in Python, v. 3.9.

	LC-EC-I	LC-EC-II	LC-EC-III	CON-EC
HFC CO ₂ flux (%)	40.5	40.3	40.1	8.8
HFC LE flux (%)	51.6	48.8	60.4	18.1
LFC CO ₂ flux (%)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.3
LFC LE flux (%)	0.4	0.1	0.9	0.3

EC-III, respectively. This indicates that the high-frequency correction accounted for 52, 49 and 60 % of the fully corrected fluxes (Table 3). The largest high-frequency attenuation was observed in the LC-EC-III setup. In contrast, the CON-EC setup exhibited a much larger slope for the only low-frequency corrected data, indicating contributions of the high-frequency correction of 9 and 18 %, respectively, for CO₂ and LE fluxes. Consequently, the high-frequency attenuation effect was reduced in the CON-EC setup as compared to the LC-EC, and it was more intense for LE than for CO₂. In contrast, the high-frequency correction exhibited similar agreement across all setups, thereby underscoring the relevance of this correction for the final fluxes. The slopes of the regressions between only high-frequency corrected data and fully corrected data were 0.99 or more in all cases, indicating that the low-frequency corrections contributed less than 1 % to the fully corrected fluxes.

3.2.4. Linear regression between LC-EC and CON-EC setups and energy balance closure

The linear regression analysis of CO₂ fluxes from LC-EC and CON-EC setups yielded slopes of 1.05, 1.0 and 0.95 for LC-EC-I, LC-EC-II and LC-EC-III, respectively (Fig. 6), with respective R² values of 0.92, 0.91 and

0.88.

For LE fluxes, the slopes were 0.99, 0.88 and 0.78 for the LC-EC-I, LC-EC-II and LC-EC-III setups, respectively, with R² coefficients of 0.85, 0.85, and 0.7, indicating higher scatter than for CO₂ (Fig. 6).

All setups in the MC plot exhibited a similar energy balance closure, with an average of 71 % across all three LC-EC setups (Table 4). At the agroforestry system (LC-EC-SRAC) where the vegetation and the tower were taller, the EBC was fully closed with 100 % of closure and with R² of 0.83.

3.2.5. Flux differences according to turbulence intensity

Fig. 7 shows the flux differences according to varying turbulent conditions, classified into three bins of u^* and σ_w . For CO₂, the relative flux differences between LC-EC and CON-EC exhibited greater variability (as indicated by the length of the whiskers) as u^* (Fig. 7a) and σ_w (Fig. 7b) increased. However, the median values remained relatively consistent, ranging from 0.8 to 1.2. The discrepancies were more pronounced for the LC-EC-III, while those for the LC-EC-I and the LC-EC-II were comparable. In the case of LE flux, the relative differences were found to be larger with increasing u^* and σ_w , as for CO₂. However, in this case the magnitude of relative flux differences was found to be larger, with values ranging from 0.6 to 1.1. The differing configurations exhibited an incremental divergence from the LC-EC-I to the LC-EC-III. Especially the LC-EC-III showed a strong underestimation of the CON-

Table 4

Energy balance closure (EBC) for the three LC-EC setups (I, II, III) and the CON-EC in the MC and the LC-EC setup at the SRAC plot.

Setup	EBC (%)	R ²
CON-EC	74	0.72
LC-EC-I	73	0.87
LC-EC-II	70	0.88
LC-EC-III	66	0.83
LC-EC-SRAC	100	0.83

Fig. 6. Correlation of CO₂ fluxes (top) and LE fluxes (bottom) from LC-EC (y-axis) versus CON-EC (x-axis), for all three low-cost setups (vertical columns) for the whole measuring campaign. The black lines represent the 1:1 line, while the red lines indicate the predicted RMA linear regression models. Additionally, the slopes, coefficients of determination (R²) and intercepts of the linear fits are presented.

Fig. 7. Box-whisker plots of relative CO₂ (a, b) and LE (c, d) flux differences between the conventional EC and the LC-EC setups, for the three LC-EC setups in the MC, depending on different u_* (top) and σ_w (bottom) classes, expressed with reference to 1.0 (a value of 1.0 indicates no difference between LC-EC and CON-EC). The boxes represent the data between the 25th and 75th percentiles, while the whiskers indicate the 5th and 95th percentiles. The horizontal black lines represent the median of each distribution. Outliers were excluded from the plots.

EC LE fluxes under all turbulent conditions, more intense for the highest u_* and σ_w classes, with values between 0.5 and 0.85.

3.2.6. CO₂ and H₂O dry mole fractions from LC-EC and CON-EC setups

The CO₂ dry mole fraction from the different LC-EC setups and the CON-EC setup demonstrated a consistent offset and a slight decline in the CO₂ dry mole fraction throughout the measurement campaign

(Fig. 8). This agreed with the observed decline of the reference ICOS station at Torfhaus (ICOS-TOH) (Kubistin et al., 2023). In the case of H₂O, the offset between setups was smaller than for CO₂; furthermore, all four setups reproduced closely the temporal variability of H₂O.

Fig. 8. Time series of 6 h averages of CO₂ (top) and H₂O (bottom) dry mole fractions, for all four setups in the MC. For comparison, CO₂ data from the ICOS atmospheric station Torfhaus (ICOS-TOH) are also presented. The data were filtered to remove outliers.

3.3. Differences in CO₂ and LE fluxes between MC and SRAC

The temporal variability of the diel cycle of CO₂ fluxes exhibited a comparable pattern between the SRAC and the MC. However, the absolute values of the CO₂ flux from the SRAC were consistently higher than those from the MC (Fig. 4a). During the nighttime, fluxes were observed to be larger (more positive) at the SRAC than at the MC by 30 %, indicating a higher CO₂ release at the site, while during the daytime, absolute values of fluxes were observed to be larger (more negative) by 29 %, indicating higher CO₂ uptake by the agroforestry system than by the MC.

The diel cycle of LE fluxes for both the SRAC and the MC plot exhibited comparable temporal variability at both plots, with low nighttime fluxes, followed by a morning increase until a maximum in the central part of the day (Fig. 4b). The LE flux was higher above the SRAC by approximately 42 % compared to the MC during the center of the day, while no clear differences were observed during the night.

The cumulative sum of the CO₂ flux expressed as grams of carbon (C) per square meter exhibited analogous trends in all the setups at the MC and the SRAC, with enhanced C sequestration at the SRAC (Fig. 9a). The cumulative C uptake increased throughout the measuring campaign until 14 July, when the harvest of the rapeseed took place. The highest C uptake rates occurred during June. Following the harvest of the rapeseed, the trend was reverted, with the fluxes turning to positive values and thus reducing C sequestration. In the mid-August, C fluxes switched again towards negative values, increasing C sequestration. The final sums indicated a net C uptake by both the MC and the SRAC, with higher values observed at the SRAC by 32 % (as a comparison between the LC-EC setup at the SRAC and the average of the three LC-EC setups at the MC). However, despite all the setups at the MC reproducing the same temporal patterns, there were clear differences across them. The LC-EC-III exhibited the lowest cumulative C uptake, while the LC-EC-I and LC-EC-II were more closely aligned, and the CON-EC demonstrated a cumulative C uptake that was comparable to that of the LC-EC-I. The discrepancy between the three LC-EC and the CON-EC final values (0, 6, and 20 g C m⁻² for the LC-EC-I, LC-EC-II, and LC-EC-III, respectively) was lower than the difference between the CON-EC and the SRAC final sum, which was 37 g C m⁻².

ET exhibited similar patterns across SRAC and MC, as well as the different setups (Fig. 9b). The cumulative ET increased throughout the entire measurement campaign, with higher ET rates observed following rain events and particularly during June. In this month, the soil had a higher moisture content than later on and the conditions for plant growth were more favorable. This may have contributed to the observed higher transpiration rates. The SRAC exhibited an ET 45 % higher than

the MC (as a comparison between the LC-EC setup at the SRAC and the average of the three LC-EC setups at the MC). The three LC-EC setups at the MC exhibited lower ET values compared to CON-EC. However, the differences between CON-EC and the LC-EC setups at the MC (3, 10 and 24 mm) were less pronounced than the differences between CON-EC and SRAC (41 mm). The difference between CON-EC and LC-EC at the MC was most pronounced for the LC-EC-III setup. The LC-EC-I setup exhibited the smallest discrepancy in ET relative to the EC setup (3 mm).

The Wasserstein metric results (Table 5) demonstrated the lowest discrepancy between LC-EC-I and CON-EC, both for CO₂ and LE fluxes, whereby the differences increased for LC-EC-II and LC-EC-III. When comparing LC-EC setups from different land uses, the Wasserstein distance for the average of the three LC-EC setups at the MC and the CON-EC was considerably smaller for CO₂ and LE than the Wasserstein distance between the average of the three LC-EC setups at the MC and the LC-EC-SRAC. Moreover, the Wasserstein distance of each pair of LC-EC setups and CON-EC setup at the MC was lower than the Wasserstein distance between the average of the three LC-EC setups at the MC and the LC-EC-SRAC. These results indicated that the discrepancies between different LC-EC setups and CON-EC were less pronounced than those between land uses (MC and SRAC).

4. Discussion

4.1. Overall performance of LC-EC compared to CON-EC

The three LC-EC setups in the MC demonstrated comparable performance to the CON-EC setup. The variability across the LC-EC setups and the CON-EC setup at the MC was lower than the difference between land uses (e.g., MC vs. SRAC) for both CO₂ and LE, which validates the initial hypothesis. The slow response time of the CO₂ and RH sensors from the LC-EC setups, which resulted in a large spectral attenuation

Table 5

Wasserstein metric computed in the following cases (i) every pair of one LC-EC setup and CON-EC at the MC, (ii) the average of all LC-EC at the MC and CON-EC at the MC, and (iii) the average of all LC-EC setups at the MC and the LC-EC at the SRAC. No normalization was applied to the metric.

	CO ₂ (μmol·m ⁻² ·s ⁻¹)	LE(W·m ⁻²)
LC-EC-I vs. CON-EC	0.44	4.1
LC-EC-II vs. CON-EC	0.59	11.6
LC-EC-III vs. CON-EC	1.11	30.9
Avg. LC-EC in MC vs. CON-EC	0.58	14.56
Avg. LC-EC in MC vs. LC-EC in SRAC	3.06	70.77

Fig. 9. Cumulative sums of (a) CO₂ fluxes and (b) ET rates, for all four setups at the MC and the LC-EC at the SRAC. In order to facilitate comparison between the different time series, only coincident periods for all setups were used for the calculation of the cumulative sums.

(see Section 4.3), was addressed by implementing an appropriate spectral correction method, a solution analogous to that proposed by Wohlfahrt et al. (2009) for a slow analyzer measuring O₃. However, as demonstrated by the cumulative sums and with the Wasserstein metric, there was a considerable degree of variability in the differences observed across setups at the MC.

The LC-EC setups exhibited comparable CO₂ flux values to those of the CON-EC, with no discernible difference (1.0 as the mean of the linear regression models depicted in Fig. 6). Conversely, they exhibited systematically smaller absolute flux values in the case of LE, with an average difference of 12.0 ± 0.1 % from the linear regression models of LE fluxes across all lower-cost setups (Fig. 6). The number of tested setups can provide an estimation of the variability and uncertainty associated with the use of LC-EC setups, compared to CON-EC, despite the low sample size of three instead of, e.g., 10. In a parallel study, it was shown that the LC-EC setup also had lower absolute values of fluxes compared to CON-EC above a grassland and a grassland SRAC site, with similar differences for both ecosystems (van Ramshorst et al., 2024). Consequently, the expectation is that the LC-EC setup at the SRAC may also underestimate the fluxes in comparison to a CON-EC if that were installed there.

4.2. Comparison to similar studies

To date, only a limited number of studies have employed LC-EC setups and compared them to conventional EC. Hill et al. (2017) compared a LC-EC setup to a conventional EC setup above a pasture field. Their results showed a very good agreement between LC-EC and conventional EC setups for both CO₂ and LE fluxes, with slopes of the linear regression models, calculated in an analogous manner to that employed in the present study, of 1.03 and 0.98 for CO₂ fluxes, and 1.06 for LE fluxes. However, while the LC-EC setup of Hill et al. (2017) used the same sensors for CO₂ and RH that were used in the current study, the conventional IRGA was open-path and the flow of their lower-cost setup was kept at higher rates than in our study, which probably helped to achieve a better agreement between LC and conventional EC in the case of LE fluxes, as it reduced spectral attenuation.

Markwitz and Siebicke (2019) showed the results of the comparison between a LC-EC setup for measuring evapotranspiration and a conventional EC setup above SRAC and MC sites. Our SRAC and the MC sites in Wendhausen were part of that study. A linear regression analysis was performed, similar to the ones shown in Fig. 6, and reported a slope of 0.99 above the SRAC site, indicating slightly lower (1 %) fluxes from the LC-EC than from the CON-EC. The remaining MC and SRAC sites showed different levels of performance, with differences between LC-EC and CON-EC ranging from 14 % underestimation to 8 % overestimation. The discrepancy in LE fluxes between the three LC-EC setups in the MC and the CON-EC setup was similar in the present study, as shown in the results section. However, in the work of Markwitz and Siebicke (2019), the same sonic anemometer was used as in our study, but a BME280 thermohygrometer sensor (Robert Bosch GmbH, Stuttgart, Germany) was employed to measure pressure, relative humidity and temperature. These data were used to derive H₂O dry mole fractions in a manner analogous to that described in the present study. The thermohygrometer was placed at a distance of 0.5 m below the center of the sonic anemometer within a PVC housing to protect it from rain, and the air flow was generated by a ventilator. The high-frequency attenuation of the H₂O dry mole fraction measurements was corrected following Moncrieff et al. (1997), which is a fully analytical formulation designed for open-path gas analyzers or short and/or heated sampling lines in closed-path analyzers (Markwitz and Siebicke, 2019). The low-frequency corrections accounted for 1 % of the fully corrected LE fluxes from the LC-EC, a magnitude similar to that observed in our study. In contrast, the high-frequency corrections accounted for 23 % of the fully corrected flux, which is a lower magnitude than in our study. This discrepancy is mainly an effect of the very short tubing system of their

setup compared to our setups, which caused less attenuation of the higher frequencies. Furthermore, our comparison was conducted at a single site, rather than across multiple locations, therefore our results could change if we averaged across multiple sites with varying characteristics and atmospheric conditions.

In a parallel study, van Ramshorst et al. (2024) performed a comparison of one LC-EC and a CON-EC setup, above a grassland and a grassland agroforestry, across different measurement campaigns. The LC-EC setup employed in this study was identical to the one used in our study, with the exception of the shorter tube lengths used in the case of the grassland site. The agreement of fluxes between the LC-EC and the CON-EC setups was very good, with slopes of the linear regression models for the CO₂ fluxes between 0.87 and 0.93 and for LE fluxes between 1.02 and 1.23 (R² from 0.84 to 0.9), comparable to our study. However, the height of the tower at the grassland site was 3 m instead of 3.5 m, which may have resulted in a greater influence of high-frequency eddies and, consequently, an enhanced tube attenuation. Furthermore, the ambient conditions during the 2021 campaign were considerably more humid than those observed during our study. This explains the inferior performance of the LC-EC setup in measuring LE fluxes due to the comparably higher RH conditions.

Some additional studies have evaluated the performance of different gas analyzers, which are typically employed in EC. One of the most comprehensive studies, conducted by Polonik et al. (2019), compared the performance of three sonic anemometers and five different gas analyzers, employing distinct spectral correction methods for CO₂ and H₂O fluxes. While the results on average did not demonstrate significant differences across setups, in some cases, particularly for H₂O fluxes, a large degree of variability was observed across different spectral correction methods and gas analyzers. In many cases, the observed differences were comparable to or larger than those presented in the current study. The slopes of the linear regression models between two different gas analyzers ranged between 0.74 and 1.36 for H₂O fluxes and 0.92 to 1.08 for CO₂ fluxes. The spectral correction methods were similar for every pair of analyzers being tested to enhance comparability. The aforementioned range of slopes would affect cumulative sums of CO₂ and ET in a similar way to that observed in our study.

4.3. Attribution of flux differences between LC-EC and CON-EC

EC measurements are subjected to different sources of errors (Finkelstein and Sims, 2001; Mahrt, 1998), which contribute to random and systematic errors. For the LC-EC setups, some of the systematic errors originate from analogous sources as those observed in CON-EC measurements. However, these newer setups have been found to exhibit enhanced systematic errors, which can be attributed to the instrumental sampling of CO₂ and RH, as well as to the poorer spectral response of the setups in comparison to CON-EC. The greater the discrepancy between the measured (co-)spectra and the actual turbulent spectrum, as shown in Section 3.2.2, the more crucial it becomes to implement spectral corrections, which inevitably introduces a greater uncertainty. Consequently, the differences observed between the LC-EC and the conventional EC setups deployed in the MC can be attributed to two distinct sources: (i) the differing spectral response of the instruments; (ii) the disparities in the sampling of CO₂ and H₂O dry mole fractions.

With respect to the first (and presumably, primary) source of error, there were significant differences in the spectral and temporal response of the CON-EC and the LC-EC setups. The LC-EC, with slower time response, was unable to measure the higher frequencies of the energy turbulent spectrum, as shown in the spectra and co-spectra plots (Fig. 5). This was observed in the co-spectra plot for unstable conditions (Fig. 5e and f) and in Fig. 7, indicating that the differences in LE and CO₂ fluxes between LC-EC and CON-EC were higher during midday when commonly more intense turbulent conditions occurred. The shape of the spectra (Fig. 5a and b) indicated a higher energy content around the peak frequency (10⁻² to 1 Hz). The significantly greater attenuation

caused by the slower CO₂ and RH sensors was evident in the more pronounced energy decrease at the inertial subrange, in comparison to the theoretical slope of -2/3 and to the energy decrease observed in both the CON-EC and the sonic temperature spectra.

This strong attenuation was illustrated in Table 4. The high-frequency corrections of the LC-EC resulted in a notable increase in the flux magnitude for both CO₂ and LE fluxes. The magnitude of the CO₂ fluxes was increased by 40 %, while that of the LE FLUXES was increased by 50 %. These values were larger than those found in other EC studies with closed-path systems, such as those reported by Ibrom et al. (2007), which observed increases of 4–5 % for CO₂ fluxes and up to 42 % for LE fluxes at the monthly scale. Similarly, Mammarella et al. (2009) reported increases of up to 30–40 % in winter and during high RH conditions for LE fluxes.

Furthermore, the low height of the tower (3.5 m), although appropriate to provide a representative footprint of the MC site (Fig. 1) led to a higher prevalence of high-frequency eddies in the spectra. This is because the tower height effect was shown to be a determinant of the spectral correction factors (Reitz et al., 2022). Fig. 5 showed that the attenuation of the co-spectra at higher frequencies was less pronounced for the LC-EC at the SRAC and this difference can be attributed to the taller tower. Despite the CO₂ and RH sensors deployed in the LC-EC setups having the same theoretical time response, fluxes across LC-EC setups were found to be different. This discrepancy can be attributed to factors such as differences in tube lengths and flow rates, which are influenced by pump performance. The tube length and flow rate are directly related to spectral attenuation, with longer tubes and lower flow rates leading to larger flux differences against the CON-EC. Furthermore, RH was typically high in the tubing system of the LC-EC setups and there were few weather events, essentially heavy rain, which subsequently led to condensation problems in the tubing system of the LC-EC setups. The high RH conditions in the tubes increase largely the spectral attenuation of H₂O and therefore LE fluxes, as studied in Fratini et al. (2012), Ibrom et al. (2007), Mammarella et al. (2009) and Massman and Ibrom (2008). Ibrom et al. (2007) recommended maintaining RH below 30 % inside the tubing system of closed-path EC setups, in order to avoid strong low-pass-filtering effects on the H₂O_v signal. In our case, RH was typically below the recommended value in the measuring cell of the IRGA, but not in the tubes. This was because only the measuring cell with the GMP343 and the HIH-4000 was heated and not the tubes (see Section 2 for the description of the setup). In any case, even if RH was below 30 % inside the measuring cell, the RH would be higher inside the tubing, thereby increasing the attenuation effect of the system.

The spectra and co-spectra exhibited marginal differences across the three LC-EC setups in the case of CO₂, which explains the minor discrepancies in the time response estimation (Table 2) and the similarities in the contribution of the high-frequency correction to the fully corrected fluxes for all setups (Table 4). In the case of H₂O, the spectra and co-spectra differed the most for the LC-EC-III setup compared to the LC-EC-I and LC-EC-II. The H₂O spectra from this setup exhibited a markedly greater attenuation at high frequencies, which could account for the considerably lower measured LE fluxes from this setup, as evidenced by the larger contribution of high-frequency attenuation in Table 4. For all three LC-EC setups, both CO₂ and H₂O spectra exhibited peaks caused by the repetition of values measured by the sensors, because the frequency response of both CO₂ and RH sensors was slower than the logging frequency of 2 Hz. This phenomenon was also observed in Eugster and Flüß (2010).

As shown in Emad (2023), Polonik et al. (2019), and van Ramshorst et al. (2024), the selected spectral correction method also incorporates a source of uncertainty. In the current study, we applied the spectral correction method of Mammarella et al. (2009) for the high-frequency range of the turbulent spectrum. In this method, the spectral analysis of H₂O is conducted for different RH classes in order to calculate the optimal transfer functions according to varying RH conditions. One distinguishing feature of the method is the use of transfer functions

derived from co-spectra, instead of spectra, in contrast to what other authors suggested (e.g. Sabbatini et al. 2018). Co-spectra are also dependent on the sonic anemometer data, in addition to LC-EC gas analyzers. This makes them less susceptible to attenuation effects from the gas analyzer than the spectra of CO₂/H₂O, which depend on concentrations (Fig. 5). However, the accuracy of the corrections also depends on the availability of long-enough datasets. The longest available dataset was that from the LC-EC-I, followed by the CON-EC, the LC-EC-II, and finally, with a much shorter dataset, the LC-EC-III. Additionally, LC-EC-III had no valid spectral data above 60 % RH (not shown). The lack of enough data, in conjunction with the explanations provided in the preceding paragraphs, account for a less optimal spectral correction performance, which is directly proportional to the differing lengths of the datasets. This phenomenon was observed in the differences observed between the LC-EC setups, despite the fact that the ensemble-averaged spectra and co-spectra did not differ significantly for the three LC-EC setups in the case of CO₂ and for the LC-EC-I and LC-EC-II in the case of H₂O.

A second potential explanation for the observed flux differences between the CON-EC and LC-EC setups can be attributed to differences in the concentration magnitudes. As illustrated in Fig. 8, there was an offset between the CO₂ mole fraction across the LC-EC setups and the CON-EC setup, as also shown by Hill et al. (2017). Additionally, CO₂ and H₂O dry mole fractions from the LC-EC setups were more noisy than those of the CON-EC, in agreement with Cunliffe et al. (2022) and Hill et al. (2017). The discrepancies in CO₂ or H₂O dry mole fraction measurements between the different setups can be attributed to inherent differences in the setup characteristics, including the sampling lines, unstable flow rates that resulted in rapid fluctuations in cell pressure, and the instrumental accuracy, as well as inaccurate calibration. Nevertheless, we suspect that there was no drift in the CO₂ or H₂O dry mole fraction signals, and the effect of noisy measurements in the covariances contributed to the random error of the setups, but not to the systematic deviation in the processed fluxes. A more precise quantification of the uncertainty associated with the setup differences is necessary in the case of the LC-EC setups in order to identify the error sources and propose methods for their correction (e.g., a different way to apply spectral corrections, especially for H₂O).

4.4. EBC analysis

The EBC at the MC and SRAC plots exhibited similar values to those observed in the EC literature, yet notable differences were evident across plots and setups. The EBC was 71 % at the MC site, as an average across the different setups, and 100 % at the SRAC site (Table 3). Eshonkulov et al. (2019) reported an EBC of 75 % for different cropland sites in southwestern Germany; Wilson et al. (2002) reported an average EBC of 84 % across 22 sites within the FLUXNET network; Stoy et al. (2013) reported a similar value (84 % ± 20 %) with EBC at cropland sites (70–78 %).

At the MC plot, EBC was found to be consistent (71 %) across all the setups, despite the lack of closure (29 % of the available energy was not measured), with similar values for the CON-EC and the LC-EC-I setups, given the highest agreement in LE flux between these two setups, and a slightly lower closure for the other two LC-EC setups. This suggests that the LC-EC setups did not necessarily misrepresent the turbulent energy fluxes, H and LE, above the MC plot, compared to the CON-EC setup.

At the SRAC plot, EBC was considerably higher than at the MC, with a perfect closure (100 %). The LC-EC setup at the SRAC differed from the LC-EC at the MC solely in terms of tower height and tube length. The observed discrepancy in the EBC across both sites can be attributed to three factors. Primarily, the effect of the measurement height on the measured turbulent spectrum must be considered. The impact of low pass filtering of an EC setup increases with decreasing measurement height, while the relevance of high-frequency spectral corrections increases. As the height decreases, the eddies become smaller in size, i.e.

closer to the surface. Thus the high-frequency range of the turbulent spectrum contributes more to the overall flux than in locations further above the surface (Reitz et al., 2022). The H₂O spectra showed an attenuation at the SRAC comparable similar to the LC-EC-I and the LC-EC-II setups at the MC, but less intense than for the LC-EC-III at the MC (Fig. 5b). However co-spectra showed a reduced attenuation at the SRAC compared to the MC (Fig. 5c–f), especially for H₂O under stable conditions, compensating for the H₂O spectral loss. The applied spectral corrections seemed to be inadequate in accounting for the height-induced attenuation at the MC, which results in a poorer EBC. Secondly, the enhanced atmospheric instability at the SRAC, with higher u^* , due to the presence of the trees. Franssen et al. (2010) showed that the largest absolute EBC deficits occur during the most stable conditions, which were observed to coincide with the highest differences in the co-spectra across SRAC and MC (Fig. 5). Thirdly, to the different flux footprint size, i.e. the higher tower led to a larger footprint area (Fig. 1), with some contributions of the measured fluxes at the SRAC originating from outside the ecosystem of interest. In addition, storage terms were not accounted for due to the lack of soil temperature or atmospheric profile data (temperature, CO₂ and H₂O mole fraction). Accounting for these terms could potentially enhance the estimation of the EBC above the studied plots, as some authors have proposed when addressing the EBC problem in EC measurements (e.g. Eshonkulov et al. 2019, Finnigan et al. 2003, Oncley et al. 2007).

4.5. Differences in CO₂ and LE fluxes between MC and SRAC

The LC-EC setups were capable of reproducing carbon and ET dynamics in both land-use systems and of discerning differences between ecosystems. We found an enhanced carbon sequestration and increased ET at the SRAC compared to the MC plot (Fig. 9). This can be attributed to the presence of fast-growing trees, which keep higher photosynthetic activity during the growing season. Markwitz et al. (2020) studied ET above several SRAC and MC sites and concluded that, despite a slightly higher ET above SRAC than above MC, land use differences (SRAC vs. MC) were smaller than differences from different years with contrasting climate conditions. To the best of our knowledge, no study has employed the EC technique to measure C fluxes above similar SRAC and MC sites, but there is evidence of an enhanced C sequestration observed at other agroforestry sites (Cardinael et al., 2015; Kay et al., 2019), which is consistent with our findings.

The higher C respiration during the nighttime did not offset the increased overall C uptake in the SRAC during the day (Fig. 4). The highest CO₂ and ET fluxes were observed in June, the month with the best-growing conditions for the crops and trees: no water limitation, moderate air temperature, and sufficient incident radiation. The harvest (14 July) of the rapeseed, located in the main footprint area, turned the ecosystem into a C source from an initial carbon sink, due to the presence of only bare soil. After that, the increased C uptake observed during the final days of the measurement campaign at both plots can be attributed to the late growth of the corn. During the measurement campaign, the SRAC sequestered more CO₂ than the MC plot, which may be a promising result for the promotion of agroforestry systems as a climate change mitigation strategy in the temperate zone.

The measurement campaign, characterized by warmer and drier periods compared to climatological averages, potentially led to plant stress for the trees and crops and subsequently reduced growth and C sequestration. However, while this was observed in several studies (e.g., Lesk et al. 2016, Martínez-Sancho et al. 2022), it remains unclear whether both SRAC and MC are equally affected by drought in terms of net primary production and water use efficiency. The measurement campaign took place during the main part of the growing season, but did not evaluate year-round fluxes and the presented data were not gap-filled. To obtain realistic ecosystem sums of C and ET it is necessary to fill gaps in the data and to conduct measurements over at least one year, in order to cover all physiological states of the ecosystems. The

enhanced C sequestration and ET at the SRAC from this study should be considered carefully until longer, gap-filled time series are analyzed.

4.6. Costs and technical feasibility of the LC-EC setups in relation to other micrometeorological methods

The total cost of the LC-EC setups, including all sensors, tubes and filters, was approximately seven thousand euros. The cost of the gas analyzer from the CON-EC setup, the Li-7200, was approximately four to five times that of the LC-EC gas analyzer. Both setups utilized the same sonic anemometer, with a cost of approximately 4000 euros. The total cost of the installation with a LC-EC setup would be 11,000 €, while for the CON-EC it would be above 40,000 €. From the other studies comparing lower-cost eddy covariance setups, Cunliffe et al. (2022) used the same design as ours and Hill et al. (2017), a very similar version, hence with similar costs; Markwitz and Siebicke (2019) used a gas analyzer enclosure with a cost of 100 €, however it only measured H₂O fluxes.

Therefore, the cost of a CON-EC gas analyzer would allow researchers to afford several LC-EC gas analyzers. This could serve to reinforce CON-EC setups or to increase the number of measuring points at the ecosystems of interest, particularly in heterogeneous sites. The technical advantages of these LC-EC setups include low power consumption, which renders them suitable for remote locations as long as the stations are fed with solar power. Additionally, the GMP343 sensor is easily calibrated and the HIH-4000 presents a long-term stability.

To the best of our knowledge, no other study has employed lower-cost EC setups for measuring gas species other than CO₂ and H₂O. However, in addition to EC, there are other micrometeorological methods which allow to quantify biosphere-atmosphere exchanges of different gas species, such as the flux-gradient method or the eddy accumulation techniques. These approaches are suitable for slow-response gas analyzers, which typically operate at a frequency lower than 1 Hz (Meyers et al., 1996). They are often employed to measure trace gases for which fast instrumentation is either unavailable or too costly (Rinne et al., 2016).

Among the eddy accumulation techniques, different approaches are relaxed eddy accumulation (REA) (Businger and Oncley, 1990), true eddy accumulation (TEA) (Desjardins, 1977) or disjunct eddy accumulation (Turnipseed et al., 2009). In recent years, several studies have been published on developing and testing new designs of these setups. Among others, Sarkar et al. (2020) compared low-cost relaxed eddy accumulation (REA) to EC measurements of biogenic volatile organic compounds (BVOC), showing a high degree of concordance between the two methods, with the low-cost REA being capable of measuring the major exchanges of BVOC above different forest sites. Emad and Siebicke (2023) compared a novel design of the TEA, termed Short True Eddy Accumulation (STEA), which overcame some of the limitations of the TEA, improving its flexibility and accuracy to be adapted to several gas species, such as reactive components. The STEA demonstrated very good performance when compared to EC. Grelle and Keck (2021) showed a satisfactory comparison of a novel version of the REA setup with reduced costs and low power requirements, as well as suitable for measuring in remote locations.

The flux-gradient method (Rinne et al., 2000) offers inexpensive measurements in relation to the EC method, however fluxes measured by this method are often subject to larger errors (Zhao et al., 2023). Some studies have compared different flux-gradient approaches to EC measurements, with satisfactory results. However, the reliability of the fluxes compared to EC varied considerably depending on factors such as atmospheric conditions, measurement height and location, or the phenological status of the ecosystems being studied (Meredith et al., 2014; Zhao et al., 2023).

Nevertheless, these and other studies provide a foundation for further improvement of the aforementioned methods, which can be considered as complementary and can help to meet the increasing

demand for reliable measurements of biosphere-atmosphere exchanges of greenhouse gases, VOCs, H₂, and other trace gas species.

5. Conclusions

We compared a set of three lower-cost eddy covariance setups to a conventional eddy covariance setup above a MC plot, as well as to a lower-cost eddy covariance setup above a SRAC plot in close vicinity to the MC plot. We presented a processing scheme that can be applied to the data measured by the LC-EC setup and we discussed the sources of uncertainties related to the LC-EC setups.

The validation of the LC-EC against the CON-EC was successful, as evidence by the fact that the differences observed across different setups were on the order of typical EC uncertainties. Furthermore, the LC-EC setups were capable of measuring differences in water and CO₂ fluxes due to different land-use types and to detect the dynamics of carbon uptake and evapotranspiration. The LC-EC setups can be employed to increase spatial replication above EC sites and as a complement to current EC measuring stations. Nevertheless, it is important to exercise caution when interpreting the results of the few studies in which the LC-EC setups were validated against conventional EC setups. The primary source of uncertainty in LC-EC measurements was the inferior spectral response of these setups in comparison to CON-EC, which resulted in the necessity of employing high spectral correction factors, particularly in the case of H₂O. In future work, we will address this issue by analyzing how the different spectral correction methods restore the attenuated eddy covariance signal.

Nevertheless, with the appropriate installation, maintenance, and the proposed processing methods, LC-EC measurements can successfully reproduce conventional EC and thus potentially help to solve some of the previously mentioned problems related to the statistical robustness and lack of replication of EC measurements. To increase the accuracy and improve the performance of the LC-EC setups, it is recommended: (i) to regularly check the flow and the functioning of the pump to keep a sufficiently high flow rate; (ii) to install a tubing system as short as possible to minimize tube attenuation effects; (iii) to regularly check and clean the measuring cell of the GMP343 IRGA; and (iv) to take special care of high RH conditions that could lead to water condensation and, hence, higher spectral attenuation. The latter could be avoided by heating the intake tubes.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

José Ángel Callejas-Rodelas: Visualization, Software, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis. **Alexander Knohl:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Justus van Ramshorst:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Ivan Mammarella:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Christian Markwitz:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

All the data used in this study are publicly available at [10.5281/zenodo.11085338](https://zenodo.org/record/11085338).

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